

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D5.1

Report on site identification and installation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice

29/07/2022

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in two selected demo sites: the Venice coastal area and the Porto region. In the demo site of Venice, the Automated Seabed Cleaning Platform has to be tested in two sites, one within the lagoon and one in the near coastal area, characterized by historically accumulated marine litter. The present report provides the identification of the demonstration sites in Venice based on data and information gathered during the implementation of WP2 for the assessment of ML pollution and state of the marine ecosystems, and the results of the installation and the pre-testing operation undertaken by TECNALIA, CNRS and ST at its facilities in Venice.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2 MAELSTROM Consortium

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3 Aim of the Deliverable

The report describes the decision-making process that leads to the identification of the demonstration sites in the Venice Coastal Area. In the demo site of Venice, the Automated Seabed Cleaning Platform has to be tested in two sites, one within the lagoon and one in the near coastal area, characterized by historically accumulated marine litter. The identification of the demonstration sites in Venice was performed on the basis of information available from previous projects and the data gathered during the implementation of the task of WP2 related to density of ML quantification. Proper permits were submitted to the competent authorities to operate both at the sea and in the lagoon waters and obtained for both areas.

Moreover, the Deliverable presents as well the results of the installation of the cable robot and its components on the floating platform and the testing operations undertaken by TECNALIA, CNRS and ST at ST facilities in Marghera and at the Arsenale in Venice.

4 Introduction

The innovative technology implemented in the demo site of Venice, i.e. the Automated Seabed Cleaning Platform, has to be tested in two locations, one in the coastal area at sea and one within the lagoon of Venice. Both areas should be characterized by historically accumulated marine litter. The identification of the demonstration sites in Venice was based on the data collected during the activities foreseen in the WP2, as well as on previous data and information available on ML presence and abundances for the Venice coastal area. In particular, the WP2 foresees that specific monitoring and assessment of ML impact on the benthic community, on the commercial fish and on shellfish species will be carried out in proximity of a mussel farm. Consequently, it was decided that, as most of the mussel farms are located at sea, the Coastal Site should be near a mussel farm concession, whereas the Lagoon Site should be characterised by the presence of urban derived litter. This choice will give us also the opportunity to test the innovative technology with completely different types of waste, improving the knowledge and the outcomes of the Project. Moreover, this decision was also supported by the results of the Deliverable 2.1. It was here highlighted that the main sources of ML characterising the Venice coastal area are related to public activities (domestic and touristic waste) and fishing-related litter both for beach and sea-floor litter.

5 Identification of the marine coastal site

Fisheries is one main maritime activity and an important economic resource in the area. The high productivity and richness in fishery resources makes the Northern Adriatic Sea the most exploited area of the Mediterranean Sea (Mazzoldi et al., 2014). The coast along the Veneto region is characterised by the presence of numerous mussel culture farms, with about 35 km² of 'exploited' area, accounting for nearly the 33% of the Italian national production. Aquaculture has been shown to contribute significantly to seafloor litter (Fortibuoni et al., 2019) and high presence of waste deriving from aquaculture activities has been already detected by various studies in the northern and central Adriatic Sea (Strafella et al., 2015; Pasquini et al., 2016; Vlachogianni et al., 2018), even in protected areas (Melli et al., 2017).

During the first year of Project activity, the Venetian Coastal Guard was contacted by CNR team to have information about possible marine litter hotspots located along the Veneto coast. The Coastal Guard provided a detailed map of the mussel farm concessions, both active and no longer operative concessions, indicating the non-operative ones as possible marine litter hotspots.

Two non-active concessions were considered for the testing of the Seabed Cleaning Platform (Figure 1):

- 1) an area in front of the Pellestrina Island, having a surface of 500.000 m², located near active mussel farms;
- 2) an area located in front of the Sile river month, having a surface of 1.960.000 m².

Figure 1 – Mussel farm concessions along the Veneto coast. In red the 2 non operative mussel farms considered as marine demo site (source Venice Coastal Guard).

Non-operational concessions have some advantages with respect to active ones for testing innovative technologies: the environment and the sea bottom are characterised by the presence of all the waste deriving from mussel farm activities, but here testing operations can be carried out without interfering with the economic activities of farming. This is important also considering the size of the platform. The attention was focused on the mussel farm located in front of the Sile river mouth.

This choice was made mainly taking into consideration the reasons listed below:

- this concession is distant from other active concessions;
- the Local Authorities asked us for an advice to define protocols to remove the waste deriving from aquaculture activities pompously abandoned by the owner on the sea-bottom from 2018;
- at present, for security reason, the area is restricted to navigation, so testing can be performed without interfering with other activities at sea;
- within this concession is still present an “Experimental Field” used from 2003 to 2010 for various research activities (see the description below);
- previous data on biological communities of the area are available due to the experimentations performed in the “Experimental Field”, that can be used as background for the ecological assessment of the MAELSTROM project.

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Moreover, during the marGnet project (www.marGnet.eu) a first investigation of the possible fate of the aquaculture material from the mussel culture farms in the Northern Adriatic Sea has been investigated through the well tested and widely employed hydrodynamic numerical model SHYFEM (Shallow Water Hydrodynamic Finite Element Model) coupled with its particle tracking module to represent the ML transport and sinking behaviour. Among the wide range of ML sources, from rivers, to ports, bathing, and touristic activities, the marGnet project focused the modelling investigation only on two specific sources: the route of fishing boats and the aquaculture plants (Ghezzi et al., 2020). This investigation has been currently extended through new more comprehensive simulations within the Task 2.3, by also including cities and main rivers as sources of ML. The preliminary scenarios delivered by the marGnet project however show that the abandoned aquaculture farm is very close to the modelled hotspots (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Particles density at the end of the simulation with the hotspot stripe along the north-western part of the Venice coastal area with the position of the one of the abandoned mussel farms (source Ghezzi et al., 2020).

5.1 Description of the mussel farm

The abandoned mussel farm is located in front of the Sile River mouth, at about 1.7 NM from the coast and it has a total surface of 1.960.000 m² (Figure 3). The area has a mean depth of about 15 m. The mussel farm was abandoned in the 2018, but the owner left at sea all the structures used to harvest mussels. For this reason, the Coastal Guard involved the CNR team to define possible solutions and protocols to clean this coastal area from the waste deriving from harvesting activities abandoned there by the concessioner.

Figure 3 – Location of the abandoned mussel farm chosen as coastal demo site.

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The most common technique adopted for mussel aquaculture at sea (offshore) is the continuous longline design. Mussel farms are usually located in areas with depths ranging from 10 to 30 m along the Veneto coast. Generally, they are maritime areas given in concessions ranging from a few ha to a maximum of 10 ha, delimited by marked buoys. Longlines consist of ropes (generally made of plastic material), with length from 100 to 300 m positioned at depth of 3-5 m (Figure 3, point 4) , supported by special buoys at regular intervals that keep the structure floating (Figure 3, point 2) and concrete or metal moorings anchored to the seabed (Figure 3, point 3). The distance between each parallel long-line is about 40 m. Mussels are stocked in tubular nets, also called “mussel socks”, having a variable length between 3 and 4 m and positioned at about 50 cm from each other (Figure 4, point 7). Ropes, nets, buoys are all made of plastic materials. Support ropes are made of polypropylene or polyester; floating buoys are made of polyester and the tubular mussel socks are made of polypropylene (Delaney E., 2016). Therefore, aquaculture and specifically mussel farming, can contribute significantly to seafloor litter, particularly if not correctly managed (Fortibuoni et al., 2019).

Figure 4 – Mussel farm, long-line system (Source Veneto Agricoltura, 2014).

A particular characteristic of this mussel farm, that led to choose it as one of the MAELSTROM study sites, is that it hosts an “Experimental field” used in the past (2003 – 2010) for research activities.

5.2 Description of the “Experimental field”

The “Experimental Field” is an area of about 5000 m² located two miles off the Cavallino coast, equipped with artificial reefs and delimited by buoys (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Location and description of the “Experimental field” (Source ARPAV, 2006).

The “Experimental Field” was a project developed in the framework of the “Three-Year Program for Environmental Protection” of the Veneto Region (1994-1996), with the financial support of the “Ministry of Environment and Territory”. It was realized by ARPAV (Regional Agency for the Environmental Prevention and Protection of the Veneto Region), in collaboration with Venice “Civil Engineers Office” and with CNR-ISMAR (National Research Council – Institute of Marine Sciences), for research activities.

The “Experimental Field” was realized to implement research activities at sea and was specifically equipped to set up and study techniques and methodologies for the protection of marine habitats, the conservation of biodiversity, fish restocking, molluscs farming and environmental monitoring (ARPAV, 2006). The area was characterized by the presence of various buoys anchored with blocks and various artificial reefs aimed to increase the productivity of the marine environment. Artificial reefs generally involve the introduction of a hard substrate to a soft bottom to increase the biological diversity of the area. In particular, the artificial reef of the “Experimental field” consisted mainly of concrete cubes and metal structures designed to prevent illegal trawling activities within the area and to create settlement surface and repopulation areas for hard substrate biological communities, including those of high economic interest. One type of artificial reef pyramids of concrete blocks of 2 m size: 4 blocks at the base and one on the top (Figure 6). Although the “Experimental field” was not used for the last 10 years, the pyramids are still present in the area.

Figure 6 – Description of the pyramids within the “Experimental field” (Source ARPAV, 2006).

The use of the “Experimental field” in the framework of the MAELSTROM project has a series of significant advantages: it allows to study the effects of the MAELSTROM innovative solution (i.e. the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform) not only on soft substrate biological communities both also on hard substrate ones, the pyramids. Moreover, previous data on biological communities on the area are available from the experiments performed in the 2010, that can be used as background for the ecological assessment.

5.3 Results on the field survey within the mussel farm

Permits to carry out MAELSTROM Project activities in the area was officially asked 15 January 2022 to the competent Authority, i.e., the Coast Guard of Jesolo. CNR obtained the permit to carry out activities in the area.

A survey was then performed in the whole area of the mussel farm in February 2022. Marine litter was mapped and classified through high resolution multibeam echosounder mapping. The whole area of the mussel farm was surveyed. The marine litter items were visually identified both on the seafloor and the water column with the help of multibeam data. Based on the obtained maps, we found in the mussel farm site at sea a high density of waste deriving from aquaculture activities on the bottom and in the water column. In particular, it was evident that all the structures of the mussel farm were abandoned in the site by the concessioner. Mapping activities highlighted the presence of various long ropes on the seafloor between the mooring blocks (Figure 7), partially sunken buoys floating in the middle of the water column (Figure 8) and the tubular nets. Moreover, the pyramids of the Experimental field” were identified as well and used for the pre-cleaning biological assessment on hard substrates (Figures 7 and 8) (see for more details the Deliverable 2.3).

The quantification of litter items was performed in the portion of the area where cleaning operations with the seabed cleaning platform will be performed. In this area, 34 mooring blocks, 10 floating buoys, 9 possible floating buoys (to be confirmed) and 25 ropes of various length (about 1.5 km of ropes) were observed (Figure 9).

Figure 7 – Results of the Multi beam mapping survey.

Figure 8 – Details of the mapping survey.

Figure 9 – Example of quantification of marine litter deriving from aquaculture activities in the seafloor of the abandoned mussel farm.

6 Identification of the lagoon site

The Lagoon of Venice is the largest wetland in the Mediterranean Basin and one of the largest in Europe, covering a surface area of around 550 km². The Lagoon is a shallow water system with an average depth of 1 m, crossed by a rather complicated net of canals (i.e. dredged channels) and covered by land for around 8% of its surface, including Venice city centre and several minor towns located on small islands. The most surface area (around 80%) consists of mud flats, tidal shallows and salt marshes, and about 11% is permanently covered by open water. The Lagoon is connected to the Adriatic Sea by three inlets: Lido, Malamocco and Chioggia, opening between its mainland marine border at south and two elongated coastal islands which are a sort of coastal strip between the Lagoon and the sea.

The Lagoon was inhabited from the most ancient times, but it was only during and after the fall of the Western Roman Empire that mainland inhabitants settled there contributing to lay the first groundwork for the foundation of the city of Venice.

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Today, besides Venice city centre, other main cities inside the Lagoon are Chioggia (at the southern inlet), Murano and Burano (in the centre of the Lagoon), Lido and Pellestrina on the two coastal islands. However, the most part of the inhabitants of Venice municipality, as well as its economic core, its airport and its harbor, stand on the north-western border of the lagoon, around the mainland towns of Mestre and Marghera. Venice has a population of about 250.000 inhabitants, of whom around 55.000 live in the historical city of Venice. To this number, one has to add the number of tourists annually visiting the city: the city received more than 13 million visitors in the year 2019, before the Covid-19 restriction (Source: <https://www.comune.venezia.it/sites/comune.venezia.it/files/immagini/Turismo/Annuario%20del%20turismo%202019.pdf>).

The evaluation of the environmental status of the Lagoon started since the 1960s, with particular focus on the central part of the basin. Indeed, this part of the Lagoon is generally considered as the most human impacted, being affected both by the industrial area on its northern edge, by the presence of Venice city centre in the middle, and by urban, touristic and commercial motor-boat traffic (Moschino et al., 2013).

A quantitative estimation of microplastics in the Lagoon environment performed in the 2012 highlighted that they tend to accumulate in mainly the inner parts of the Lagoon, showing a behaviour similar to that of other contaminants (Vianello et al., 2013). It is well known that secondary microplastics, deriving from the fragmentation of larger items, are the main fraction of microplastics in the marine environments. Consequently, these data could be used as proxy also for possible accumulation hotspot of macro-litter in the Lagoon of Venice. Marine macro-litter is present throughout the floor of the channels though with highly variable concentrations mainly depending on the economic activities in the adjacent area. An assessment of the spatial distribution of the marine macro-litter performed in the 2013 in the full area of the Venice Lagoon tidal channels and inlets estimated an average density of to 7.5 items/km², the highest litter concentration occurring around the cities of Venice and Chioggia. In particular, in the Grand Canal, the highest value of mean abundance of marine litter on the sea-floor was found (1161 items/km²) (Madricardo et al., 2019).

Most recently, in the framework of the EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12/S2/05/SI2.789314 MarGnet Project (Mapping and recycling of marine litter and ghost nets on the sea-floor), the area of Sacca Fisola was monitored in the 2019 and a ML hotspot was found. An area of 0.095 km² was surveyed and 283 objects on the seafloor subdivided in 5

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categories were identified: tires (122), piles (86), crates (9), boats (8) and unknown (58) (Madricardo et al., 2020).

Based on this previously available information, two possible sites were identified within the Lagoon of Venice to test the MAELSTROM innovative technology, i.e. the Seabed Cleaning Platform:

- Grand Canal, the main navigation channel within the city center of Venice;
- Sacca Fisola, located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical centre.

For logistic reasons, Sacca Fisola was chosen as demo site for the main cleaning survey. Navigation is restricted along the Grand Canal, and operating the platform within the Grand Canal could be more difficult considering its size and the high boat traffic of the canal. Moreover, it was considered that it would have been easier to get the permits to work at Sacca Fisola rather than at the Grand Canal. However, discussions are ongoing with the Municipality of Venice to operate the Seabed Cleaning Platform also in the Grand Canal

6.1 Description of Sacca Fisola

Sacca Fisola Island is located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical centre of Venice (Figure 10). Sacca Fisola is an artificial island, created in the 1960s. From 1969 to 1984 Sacca San Biagio, another small artificial island connected to Sacca Fisola, housed an incinerator for municipal solid waste. After the closure and demolition of the incinerator, the area was cleaned. The area still hosts the Veritas (the Venice waste management company) worksite, where waste is delivered daily.

Figure 10 – Location of Sacca Fisola, the Lagoon site.

6.2 Results on the field survey within the Lagoon site

Permits to carry out MAELSTROM Project activities in the area was officially asked 11 February 2022 to the competent Authority, i.e. Provveditorato Interregionale per il Veneto, Trentino AA, Friuli Venezia Giulia. CNR obtained the permit to carry out activities in the area.

A survey was then performed in the south part of Sacca Fisola in November 2021 (Figure 11). Marine litter was mapped and classified through high resolution multibeam echosounder mapping, to identify ML on the seafloor. Moreover, a dedicated workflow in ArcGIS was developed to extract the litter items starting from the high-resolution Digital Terrain Model (DTM) (5-10 cm horizontal resolution) extracted from the bathymetry data. It consists of six different steps and uses different ArcGIS tools run recursively. A dedicated Research Object containing the workflow and more information was developed in the RoHub Research object management platform in synergy with the activities of the H2020 RELIANCE (REsearch Lifecycle mAnagement for Earth Science Communities and CopErnicus users in EOSC) project. At the same time, drop frames and pictures from the seafloor as ground truth were collected (see for more details the Deliverable 2.3).

Figure 11 – Location of Sacca Fisola, the Lagoon site.

Based on the obtained maps, we found at Sacca Fisola a high density of waste deriving from urban activities on the channel bottom such as tyres (n=177), poles (n=18)

and others (n=264, such as small sunken boats, crates). A total number of 459 items was observed in a surveyed area of 0.03 km² (Figure 12).

The observed litter on the sea-floor of the channel could derive from accidental loss from boat operating in the area (for example tyres are used as fenders on boat used to transport goods, Figure 13) or from illegal dumping at sea.

Figure 12 – Example of quantification of marine litter deriving from urban activities in the channel seafloor.

Figure 13 – Typical boat used in Venice to transport goods with tyres as fender.

7 Assessment of the tidal and current regime in the two cleaning sites

For the chosen sites, thanks to the high-resolution hydrodynamic finite element model SHYFEM, we extracted the main physical parameters needed for the design of the seabed-cleaning platform. The model simulated the water circulation and tidal level in the Venice Lagoon and coastal area for the year 2019. Real tidal and meteorological conditions were used to force the model. The discharge of the main rivers is included in the model, whereas no baroclinic circulation and waves were considered. This means that the values could be underestimated in case of storms and rainfall regime. The following analysis represents an explorative assessment of the simulated data.

7.1 Results of the hydrodynamic model within the coastal marine site

For the marine coastal site, an indicative point at depth of 14.35 m with coordinates 12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N was selected. In this point, the model has twelve levels in depth: L1 = 0.6 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5 m, L4= 4.5 m, L5= 5.5 m, L6= 6.5m, L7=7.5m, L8=8.5 m, L10=9.5 m, L11=11 m, L12=13.17 m.

The results of the simulation of the water level over the whole 2019 year are depicted in Figure 14, where the level ranges between a minimum of -0.53 m in February to a maximum 1.69 m in November.

Figure 14 – Simulated water level at the point of coordinates (2.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) over the year 2019.

The water level ranges from a minimum of -0.52 m to a maximum of 1.96 m with the following percentile distribution (Table 1):

Table 1 – Water level percentiles distribution at the marine coastal site

Percentiles	Water level (m)
5	-0.1391
25	0.1502
50	0.3729
75	0.5621
90	0.7262

For the same point, we extracted the current values over time for the twelve water levels. Timeseries of current speed in each layer is show in Figure 15.

Figure 15 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) over the year 2019 in the twelve water depth levels (L1= 0.6 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5 m, L4= 4.5 m, L5= 5.5 m, L6= 6.5m, L7=7.5m, L8=8.5 m, L10=9.5 m, L11=11 m, L12=13.17 m).

Maximum speed and percentile of currents [m] were calculated on each layer (see Table 2). The maximum current is at the surface with a value of 0.99 m/s.

Table 2 – Maximum speed and percentile of currents for each water level.

	Water levels (m)											
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12
Max Speed	0.99	0.8	0.64	0.51	0.40	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.3	0.29	0.31

Percentile	5	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
	25	0.15	0.09	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02
	50	0.24	0.15	0.09	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.03
	75	0.36	0.24	0.14	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.04
	90	0.51	0.35	0.23	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.05

The distribution of the current direction are reported in Figure 16. On the top layer the main direction is southward along the coast.

Figure 16 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) over the year 2019 in the twelve water depth levels (L1= 0.6 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5 m, L4= 4.5 m, L5= 5.5 m, L6= 6.5m, L7=7.5m, L8=8.5 m, L10=9.5 m, L11=11 m, L12=13.17 m).

7.2 Analysis for July and August 2019

Since the platform will be tested mostly during the summer period, in the following section we focussed on the July and August months. In particular, the water level timeseries were reported in Figure 17.

The Water level ranges from a minimum -0.41 m to a maximum of 0.98 m in the period July-August 2019. The percentiles do not differ much from the yearly values.

Figure 17 – Simulated water level at the point of coordinates (12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) in July and August 2019.

In Table 3 the maximum current speed values reached in each layer are reported together with the percentile calculation.

Table 3 – Maximum speed and percentile of currents for each water level for the period July-August.

		Water levels (m)											
		L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12
Max Speed		0.85	0.67	0.53	0.39	0.30	0.28	0.29	0.28	0.27	0.24	0.22	0.16
Percentile	5	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
	25	0.16	0.10	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02
	50	0.24	0.15	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.03
	75	0.33	0.22	0.13	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.04
	90	0.42	0.30	0.19	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.05

The Figure 18 illustrates the timeseries of current speed for each layer during the period July-August 2019, whereas in Figure 19 the distribution of current directions in the period July-August are shown.

Figure 18 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) over July and August 2019 in the twelve water depth levels (L1= 0.6 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5 m, L4= 4.5 m, L5= 5.5 m, L6= 6.5m, L7=7.5m, L8=8.5 m, L10=9.5 m, L11=11 m, L12=13.17 m).

Figure 19 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.5927792 E, 45.4521599 N) over July and August 2019 in the twelve water depth levels (L1 = 0.6 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5 m, L4= 4.5 m, L5= 5.5 m, L6= 6.5m, L7=7.5m, L8=8.5 m, L10=9.5 m, L11=11 m, L12=13.17 m).

7.3 Results of the hydrodynamic model within the Lagoon site

For the Lagoon site, an indicative point at depth of 3.53 m with coordinates 12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N was selected. In this point, the model has four levels in depth: L1 = 0.5 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5m, and L4= 3.26 m.

The results of the simulation of the water level over the whole 2019 year are depicted in Figure 20: the level ranges between a minimum of -0.53 m in February to a maximum 1.69 m in November.

Figure 20 – Simulated water level at the point of coordinates (12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N) over the year 2019.

It is important to know how much the water level changes in the channel in order to understand the operability condition of the platform. In the following Table 4 the water level percentiles distribution are listed. For most of the time, the water level is over 0.3 m.

Table 4 – Water level percentiles distribution at Sacca Fisola

Percentiles	Water level (m)
5	-0.1529
25	0.1612
50	0.3763
75	0.5832
90	0.7453

For the same point, we extracted the current values over time for the four water levels. Timeseries of current speed in each layer is show in Figure 21. Note that the scale are different.

Figure 21– Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N) over the year 2019 in the four water depth levels L1 = 0.5 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5m, and L4= 3.26 m.

Maximum speed and percentile of currents [m] were calculated on each layer (see Table 5). The maximum current is at the surface with a value of 0.266 m/s.

Table 5 – Maximum speed and percentile of currents for each water level.

		Water levels (m)			
		L1	L2	L3	L4
Max Speed		0.27	0.25	0.19	0.12
Percentile	5	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01
	25	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.02
	50	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.02
	75	0.12	0.10	0.07	0.03
	90	0.14	0.12	0.09	0.04

The main direction of the current follows the channel axes. Figure 22 reports the distribution of the current directions on each layer. The bimodal distribution of the direction according to the tidal regime.

Figure 22 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N) over the year 201-9 in the four water depth levels L1 = 0.5 m, L2=1.6 m, L3=2.5m, and L4= 3.26 m.

7.4 Analysis for July and August 2019

Since the platform will be tested mostly during summer, in the following section we focussed on the July and August months. In particular, The water level timeseries are reported in Figure 23.

Figure 23 – Simulated water level at the point of coordinates (12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N) Juòy and August 2019.

The Water level ranges between a minimum -0.37 m and a maximum of 1.02 m in the period July-August 2019: The percentiles do not differ much from the yearly values.

Also, the current distribution in these two months do not differ much from the yearly values. In the Table 6 the maximum current speed values reached in each layer are reported together with the percentile calculation.

Table 6 – Maximum speed and percentile of currents for each water level for the period July-August.

		Water levels (m)			
		<i>L1</i>	<i>L2</i>	<i>L3</i>	<i>L4</i>
<i>Max Speed</i>		0.25	0.21	0.17	0.09
<i>Percentile</i>	<i>5</i>	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
	<i>25</i>	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.02
	<i>50</i>	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.02
	<i>75</i>	0.12	0.11	0.07	0.03
	<i>90</i>	0.14	0.13	0.10	0.05

The Figure 24 illustrates the timeseries of current speed for each layer during the period.

Figure 24 – Simulated currents at the point of coordinates (12.3114100 E, 45.4247360 N) over July and August 2019 in the four water depth levels L1 = 0.5 m, L2 = 1.6 m, L3 = 2.5 m, and L4 = 3.26 m.

The distribution of current directions in each layers are reported in figure . The bimodal distribution of the direction is confirmed also in this period.

8 Installation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice

The Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Cable Robotics has been designed, manufactured, assembled and validated at Tecnalia facilities in collaboration with CNRS-LIRMM. The description of these activities has been reported in Deliverable D3.1 "Report on the cable robot design and teleoperated control".

Figure 25 – Underwater cable robot assembled at Tecnalia facilities

Figure 26 – Detailed view of the mobile platform of the underwater cable robot assembled at Tecnalia facilities

After being validated at Tecnalia facilities, the prototype has been sent to ST facilities in Porto Marghera and it was ready for its assembly on the floating barge provided by ST.

Figure 27 – ST facilities in Porto Marghera (Venice)

Next you can see the pontoons connected at Porto Marghera.

Figure 28 – Pontoons of the floating barge in Porto Marghera ready for the assembly of the Underwater Cable Robot

8.1 Brief description of the components of the Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Cable Robotics

The Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Cable Robotics are composed of the following components:

- Metallic posts (4 units) where the winches and the pulleys are fixed to;
- 8 sets of cable routing elements: pulleys are used to route the cables for the winch to the mobile platform; force sensors will be placed at one of the routing pulleys to measure the cable tensions; 8 force sensors will be used, one per cable;
- 8 cables attached to the mobile platform, and which drive the mobile platform motion and/or constrain part or all of the platform degrees of freedom;
- 8 synchronous winches that are used to control the length of the cables;
- Underwater mobile platform frame where the cables are attached to and where the grippers and perceptions sensors are integrated in;
- Umbilical cable for power and data feeding to the platform;
- Electrical cabinet containing the power (drive, amplifier, converter, etc.) and control (computer, fieldbus interface, etc.) required for the winch motors;
- Control room where the master computer, the main electrical cabinet and the operator(s), responsible for the safety and for the proper operation of the machine, are located;
- Floating barge based on pontoons where the metallic posts, control room, crane, and other equipment is mounted on;
- A crane on the barge, hoisting a basket from the surface. The crane deposits the basket on the seabed and the cable robot makes the fine manipulation of the objects to be deposited in the basket. When full, the basket is lifted on the floating barge.

The underwater cable robot has been patented by TECNALIA on 26th May 2022 - EP22382506.8- "Underwater cable robot". The innovation of the solution is focused on the decision of where to locate the winches and the pulleys in the floating barge and on the design of the underwater robot frame with the aim of filling the requirements of the application that are the following:

- Maximize the working space of the cable robot mounted on the floating barge (for pulleys must be as open as possible) at different depths of the water column and at seabed;
- Operability of the cable robot: ease of assembly, set-up and maintenance + cable robot out of the water for transporting the floating barge from spot to

Figure 30 – Overall description of the underwater cable robot system

Figure 31 – CAD 3D design of the whole Maelstrom Seabed Cleaning Platform based on cable robotics: main gripper activated

Figure 32 – CAD 3D design of the whole Maelstrom Seabed Cleaning Platform based on cable robotics: aspiration system activated

8.2 Preparation of the floating barge

Floating barge is composed of rigidly connected pontoons whose size are 24,500 mm x 12,250 mm. The floating barge is designed for still waters and sea operations. The maximum depth of operation is directly correlated to the width of the floating barge. The stability of the floating barge is ensured by anchored feet or wire anchors, depending on the depth of the cleaning, to the seafloor. The floating barge is transported from spot to spot by a tugboat. The maneuverability of the barge will be the responsibility of the tug master and the characteristics of the tug, that will be approved from the harbor master for the selected navigation zones

A crane will be mounted on the barge, hosting a basket from the surface. The crane deposits the basket on the seabed and the cable robot makes the fine manipulation of the objects to be deposited in the basket. When full, the basket is lifted onto the floating barge.

The final design of the pontoons and interfaces for assembly of the posts of the cable robot is shown next.

Figure 33 – CAD 3D of the final design of the floating barge

Figure 34 – Drawings of the final design of the floating barge

The floating barge is composed of 7 pontoons rigidly connected and by an area of compensation formed by floating raft and steel plates.

Figure 35 – Photo of the pontoon with additional bases for mounting the metallic posts

Figure 36 – Compensation area of the floating barge mounted by ST (Venice)

8.3 Installation of the metallic posts and control rooms

The four metallic posts have been transported with the winches, pullies and sensors assembled. Thanks to that, their assembly on the pontoons has taken only a short time. Next, several photos taken during their assembly are shown.

Figure 37 – Mounting the metallic posts and the main control room on the floating barge by ST and TECNALIA people

8.4 Installation of the generator and electrical wiring

Next, the generator has been installed and the electrical wiring between the 4 metallic posts and the electrical cabinets has been performed.

Figure 38 - Electrical wiring of the 4 metallic posts to the electrical cabinet and generator.

The electrical cabinets are located inside the main control room. There are three electrical cabinets: the main electric cabinet where the drives of synchronous motors and the variators of the motors of the vertical carriages of the metallic posts are, the electric cabinet for the PLC of the cable robot and the electric cabinet for the main gripper. Next, you can see the inside of the main control room.

Figure 39 - Electrical cabinets in the main control room.

Once the wiring is finished, the generator is switched on. The next step is to check the movements of the vertical carriages of the metallic posts and the winches. All the motors work perfectly.

8.5 Installation of underwater mobile platform

Next step is to attach the cables to the underwater mobile platform.

On one side, the main aspiration tube, the main gripper, the 5 IP cameras, the lights and the main capsule with the electronics are mounted on the underwater mobile platform. On the other side, biodegradable grease has been applied generously to

each steel cable. After that, the cables are attached to the underwater mobile platform one by one. Finally, the cables are tensed. The underwater cable robot is already mechanical and electrically assembled. The robot is ready for its calibration.

Figure 40 - Process of mounting the underwater mobile platform

Figure 41 - Process of connecting the cables to the underwater mobile platform

Figure 42 - Underwater cable robot assembled on the floating barge by ST and TECNALIA staff.

8.6 Calibration of the underwater cable robot

Once the Underwater cable robot has been fully assembled, it has been calibrated using a total station following the next steps:

1. Prepare an absolute reference visible from the side and front, on which to work with measurements made from different positions of Total Station.

Figure 43 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: absolute reference

We decide to use 3 targets planned to measure the A_i points as reference points. Lower targets of pulleys A2, A7 and A3 are suitable because they are all at the same

level and vector 2 to 7 is aligned with the legitimate X axis of robot frame. Therefore vector 2 to 7 directly forms the X axis and the normal of 2-7-3 plane forms the Z axis. Y axis is the result of Z by X cross product.

The origin of robot frame is the intersection between the parallel of vector 2 to 7 passing through the middle of segment 7-3 and the parallel of vector 7 to 3 passing through the middle of segment 2-7. It is at the same level (in Z) as the target.

Figure 44 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: Robot frame definition

2. Measure the A_i points

The A_i points coordinates are calculated with the help of reflective targets measured by the total station:

Figure 45 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: Calculation of A_i points from the target measurements

Thanks to the robot frame defined in step 1, the A_i coordinates are the followings:

Base points (m)	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	A_8
X	-4.5302	-5.2497	-5.2745	-4.5511	4.4993	5.2194	5.2503	4.5299
Y	-3.6719	-3.6695	3.6491	3.6472	3.6504	3.6466	-3.6695	-3.6732
Z	0.2201	0.2226	0.2247	0.2173	0.2365	0.2412	0.2241	0.2215

3. Define the B_i coordinates

The platform calibration has been performed at the Tecnolia facility. As it is an undeformable part, we can keep the same value for B_i coordinates

Figure 46 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: reference frame definition and cable exit points B_i

The B_i coordinates in the platform frame are the followings:

Platform points (m)	B_1	B_2	B_3	B_4	B_5	B_6	B_7	B_8
X	0.7190	-0.6034	-0.7372	0.6073	-0.7190	0.6008	0.7367	-0.6106
Y	-0.7191	0.4546	-0.6491	0.4626	0.7191	-0.4565	0.6490	-0.4587
Z	0.0118	0.4803	0.0020	0.4828	-0.0118	0.4996	-0.0059	0.4953

4. Suspend the moving platform from the cables and bring it to a centred position of the work volume, with the carriages in the upper position.
5. Measure the 3 reference points of the robot frame and the 3 reference points on the platform to calculate the initial pose of the platform into the robot frame.

Figure 47 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: 3 reference points on the platform

Figure 48 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot: measuring the Leica stickers in Ai and Bi points

Figure 49 - Calibration of the Underwater Cable Robot by TECNALIA

8.7 Radio controller and HMI of the underwater cable robot

All the movements and rotations of the cable robot and the vertical carriages of the metallic posts are controlled with the radio controller. Also, the gripper and the aspiration can be commanded from the radio controller: open – close and rotation of the main gripper can be commanded as well as the ON / OFF of the aspiration tube and the hydraulic cylinder to go up and down the end part of the aspiration tube.

Figure 50 - Radio controller of the Underwater Cable Robot

Next The MAELSTROM -Web based HMI (Client/Server architecture) can be seen:

Figure 51 - MAELSTROM -Web based HMI (Client/Server architecture)

MAELSTROM GUI description

- Area 1: Winch Axis information Area: Motor encoder position, speed, power and motion status.
- Area 2: Secondary Commands. These commands buttons are for setting up proposal and include:
 - Individual & grouped motion for cables without transformation activated.
 - Motion command to calibration position (Init).
 - Enable Towers motion movements from joystick.
- Area 3: Robot Pose information Area: Relative to Robot Frame in meters and radians.
- Area 4: Manual commands area including:
 - Initialization. Calculation of the Cartesian Pose (Forward kinematics)
 - Manual move from joystick enabling & speed override setting.
 - Robot Status
- Area 5: Automatic command area including:
 - PTP motion command (Actual to Destination Pose).
 - CNC trajectory program execution
- Area 6: Cable Tension monitoring area . Sensor values in Kg

Next, the MAELSTROM screen for seeing the images taken by 5 IP cameras:

Figure 52 - MAELSTROM -screen for seeing the images taken by the 5 IP cameras

The IP cameras are located on the base of the underwater mobile platform as you can see in the following images.

Figure 53 - Location of the 5 IP cameras in the underwater robot frame

The distance between the IP cameras and the lowest part of the gripper is 516 mm, that means that the visibility of the water needed to use the cameras must be higher than 516 mm or we must put closer the cameras to the lowest part of the gripper.

Figure 54 - Main distances of the Bi points and IP cameras of the underwater robot frame with respect to the gripper and the Ai points

8.8 Verification of the movement of the underwater cable robot out of the water

Once the underwater cable robot was calibrated, TECNALIA staff proceeded to the integration and set-up of the kinematics of the cable robot and to check the cartesian movement and rotations of the mobile platform. PLC and CNC of the cable robot are checked.

Then, TECNALIA verified the operation of the cable robot out of the water; they checked the movement of the cable robot and defined the limits of the workspace.

Figure 55 - Verification of the limits of the workspace of the underwater Cable Robot

Figure 56 - Verification of the rotations of the underwater Cable Robot.

8.9 Verification of the movement of the underwater cable robot under the water

Next, TECNALIA has verified the operation of the cable robot under the water; they have checked the movements and rotations of the cable robot and defined the limits of the workspace.

Figure 57 - Verification the operation of the underwater Cable Robot under water (max depth 2.3 m)

8.10 Integration and connection of the main gripper

The main gripper is hydraulically activated. Next, you can see the hydraulic equipment. 4 pipes have been connected to the main gripper to control the opening and closing and the rotation. Another 2 pipes have been connected to hydraulic cylinder to go up and down the aspiration tube.

Figure 58 - Hydraulic equipment and electrical cabinet for the main gripper and hydraulic cylinder.

The operation of gripper can be commanded from the radio controller: open, close and rotation.

Figure 59 - Operation of the gripper checked: open, close and rotation.

Figure 60 - First object picked by the gripper.

Next you can see the umbilical cable covered with a plastic protection. The umbilical cable includes the cable for transmitting power and communication to the underwater mobile platform and the hydraulic pipes for the main gripper and the hydraulic cylinder. Several buoys have been fixed to maintain the umbilical cable on the surface and avoid collision with any marine object/rocks under the water. It is important to remember that the gripper MUST be closed to activate the aspiration system.

Figure 61 - Umbilical cable protected and buoys added for guaranteeing its safety.

8.11 Integration and connection of aspiration system

Next you can see the photos of the aspiration/suction system mounted on the mobile platform. The last part of the aspiration tube is telescopic and its vertical movement is performed with an hydraulic cylinder.

Figure 62 - Aspiration system: Telescopic end – up and down positions.

8.12 Integration and connection underwater perception sensors

The robotic platform embeds the so-called “smart-camera”. The smart camera is inside a 6-inch-wide underwater enclosure, and it includes:

- A **high sensitivity usb camera** looking downwards to provide a seabed's view, in order to detect the waste.
- A **Jetson NX2 Xavier computer board** in which will be implemented the Artificial Intelligence algorithm in charge of automatically detecting the waste.
- A Blue Robotics Bar30 **High-Resolution Depth/Pressure Sensor**, allowing to accurately measure the depth of the smart camera with respect to the sea surface.
- A Bosch BNO055 9-dof **MEMS IMU (Micro ElectroMechanical – Inertial Measurement Unit)** allowing to estimate the orientation of the smart camera (pitch and roll), to make the localization of the waste more accurate.

- An **Arduino MKR ZERO microcontroller board associated to a MKR Ethernet shield**, used to interface the pressure sensor and the IMU with the surface computer at a frequency of 20 Hz (sampling period = 50 ms) over Ethernet (UDP).

Figure 63 - On the left picture: the underwater platform with the smart camera attached to the side. On the right picture: the top part of the smart camera's enclosure.

A **Doppler Velocity Log (DVL)** (DVL A50 Waterlinked, 1MHz) is also connected to the smart camera, in order to acoustically measure the distance between the camera and the seabed (along four narrow acoustic beams) and also to measure the speed of the platform with respect to the seabed. The update rate of the DVL depends on the covered distance and is about 10 Hz. These data will be used for bathymetric purposes (see later in this document), as well as for the advanced control of the robot (in another work package). All the electronic hardware and software related to the smart camera and its set of sensors (including the DVL) has been developed by the LIRMM-CNRS.

On the barge, we installed also **two RTK GPS**, located on the top of two posts located at extremities of the barge. These GPS provide the accurate geographic position and orientation (heading) of the barge. This is necessary to build a georeferenced map of the area, including the bathymetric data and the location of the waste detected by the smart camera. The software of the GPS has been designed by Tecnalía, while the frame conversion, as well as heading estimation, has been developed by the LIRMM-CNRS.

We also installed **two IMUs (one on each side floater of the barge)**, to measure the **attitude (pitch and roll)**, as well as the **rate of turn**, of the floaters (floating pontoons) supporting posts and winches of the cable robot. These data will be used for the control of the robot to compensate for the differential motions of the side floaters of

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the barge, which modify all the time the geometric configuration of the robot. During our stay in Venice, we collected some samples of orientation/rate of turns, to be able to statistically estimate the amplitude of the disturbances. This will allow us to better anticipate the potential negative effects of the swell on the behavior of the robot. This will be useful for the next work packages. The hardware of the IMUs has been developed by Tecnalio, while the software has been developed by the LIRMM-CNRS.

Figure 64 -The rear starboard post of the cable robot. One can see one of the pulleys, the winch, the position of the RTK GPS antenna, and the common enclosure of the IMU and barometer.

On the barge, we also installed **a barometer**, to measure the atmospheric pressure in real time. This is used in the depth measurement to compensate for the atmospheric pressure changes during the days. Indeed, the smart camera's depth sensor measures the sum of the pressure due to the water column above it, and due to the atmospheric pressure above the water surface. Atmospheric pressure variations can lead to depth errors greater than 30 to 40 cm (in fact 1hPa corresponds to the pressure variation of 1 cm of water). Subtracting the real atmospheric pressure to the

pressure measured by the depth sensor allows to make this measurement independent of the weather conditions. We implemented and also successfully tested this feature.

During the experiments in July, we also tested and improved **the mapping/navigation software and its Graphic User Interface** (Figure 66) designed by LIRMM-CNRS (in the framework of Cyril Barrelet's PhD thesis). This software collects, synchronizes, records, and displays all the data from the above-mentioned sensors, and from the cable robot. Based on the RTK GPS measurements, it also makes the frames' conversions to compute the geographic coordinates of the positions of every depth measurement made by the DVL beams. These bathymetric data are stored in a georeferenced 100 m x 100 m wide map (this size can be changed if needed). The local depth map, under the robot, is computed and updated from the georeferenced map after each GPS measurement and it is displayed in the GUI to provide an easy interpretable view of the bathymetry. This map also prevents the robot from colliding with the bottom. The user can also click on the map to automatically navigate to a desired position, where waste is located. Another possibility to reach the waste is to click on the picture from the smart camera. Then, the GUI computes the coordinates of the target in the robot's frame. Then the GUI transfers these coordinates to the robot and this latter automatically moves to the target.

Figure 65 - A screenshot of the Graphic User Interface (GUI) of the mapping and navigation software, tested and improved in Venice. On the left, one can see the bathymetric map, in the middle, the data from the sensors, and on the right, the video from the smart camera displayed in real time.

The GUI software is also able to **generate exploration trajectories** to perform the mapping of the site when this latter is visited for the first time. Then the robot “scans” the area with the DVL and the data from the DVL are filtered to remove the acoustic outliers. In fact, occasional erroneous measurements occur because of the multiple acoustic paths between the DVL, the seabed and the sea surface. This filtering was also tested and improved in July in Venice.

Furthermore, the software also estimates the tide level in real time, without requiring any data from a shore tidal station.

During the tests in ST facilities, we also performed the calibration of the magnetometers of the IMU, and the optical calibration of the smart camera (Figure 67).

Figure 66 - The optical calibration of the underwater smart camera. On the right, the pictures of the target used during the calibration process.

The optical calibration has been done without difficulty, whereas, as expected, the metallic barge, as well as the iron frame of the platform, created a significant magnetic disturbance, that neither hard iron, nor soft iron calibration of the magnetometers could compensate for. This resulted in the fact that the magnetic measurement of the heading was not possible on the underwater platform. This problem has been solved by computing the heading from the differential positions of the two RTK GPS.

8.13 Safety components in the floating platform

Safety measurements have been implemented in the floating platform:

- Fences to define the accessible areas to operators of the seabed cleaning platform
- Stairs to go into and out of the floating platform
- Floating raft for maintenance operations in the underwater seabed
- Wooden plates over the bases of the posts

Figure 67 - Safety measurements on the Seabed cleaning platform

8.14 Seabed cleaning platform mounted and validated at the Arsenale Pending points and riks for the cleaning campaigns

Once the seabed cleaning platform based on cable robotics was assembled and validated it was moved by 2 boats from Porto Marghera (Venice) to the Arsenale (Venice).

Figure 68 - Seabed cleaning platform during its transportation from Porto Marghera to the Arsenale (Venice)

Figure 69 - Seabed cleaning platform based on cable robotics at the Arsenale (Venice)

Figure 70 - Seabed cleaning platform based on cable robotics ready for cleaning at the Arsenale (Venice)

Figure 71 - TECNALIA, CNRS-LIRRM and ST teams at the Arsenale (Venice)

The whole system was tested again, however, there are still the following pending points needs to be taken into account before the start of the cleaning that will take place on September 2022:

- The aspiration system was not working properly yet during the tests in July and no marine litter aspiration testing could be carried out.
- The crane and underwater basket have not yet been delivered, integrated, and tested in interaction with the cable robot.
- Due to the date of having all the systems integrated in the underwater cable robot, it was possible to grab just once 1 artificial object that placed on the seafloor for the tests. Therefore, at this stage, it is not possible yet to say that the whole seabed cleaning platform has been fully validated.
- The correct functioning of the cable robot at high depths has not been tested yet. Tests at Porto Marghera were done at 2.3 depth and in the Arsenale at 5 m depth.
- The ADCP current sensor has not yet been integrated and tested.
- Bathymetry maps have not been used yet. Coordinates of the RTK-GPS have not yet been correlated with the bathymetry maps but this will be done in the

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beginning of August. The accuracy of the bathymetry maps should be in the range of few centimetres.

- The visibility in Sacca Fisola is much worse than expected; the visibility is around 20-25 cm whereas the vision cameras are at 52 cm from the lower area of the gripper. We must put closer the cameras to the lower area of the gripper or trust on the bathymetry maps and use them for commanding the robot to the location of the marine litter to be removed
- The visibility in “Experimental Field” is not known yet.
- In the “Experimental Field” the aim is to remove ropes, however, the underwater cable robot has been designed to remove single objects like tyres, containers, boxes, bottles, tins,...) not continuous objects as ropes, so it may be necessary to develop a system to cut the ropes or have the support of the divers for that.

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